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Research article

Parvovirus B19 is the cause of thyroid cancer

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Abstract:

Background:

The null-hypothesis: human parvovirus B19 is not the cause of human thyroid cancer has been tested.

Methods:

To examine the possible role of parvovirus B19 infection in the aetiology of human thyroid cancer, a literature searched through the electronic database PubMed was performed. Data were accurately assessed and reanalysed by new statistical methods.

Results:

The meta-analysis results of this study provide evidence that a parvovirus B19 infection of thyroid tissues and human thyroid cancer are causal related. The null-hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion:

The alternative hypothesis: human parvovirus B19 is the cause of human thyroid cancer is accepted (p Value right tailed (HGD)= 1,85004E-05).

Keywords: Parvovirus B19; Thyroid cancer; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k

1. Introduction

Very little is known about the aetiology of thyroid cancer. Several risk factors such as high dietary iodine intake, thyroid irradiation, autoimmune diseases, genetic alterations (see Schlumberger, 1998) and others including infectious agents too have been implicated with thyroid cancer. Human parvovirus B19 (B19) or “Nakatani” virus (see Okochi et al., 1984), discovered 1974 by Cossart et al. (see Cossart et al., 1975), is such an infectious agent which belongs to the large Parvoviridae (see Adams et al., 2014) family. B19 is a small, non-enveloped, linear, single-stranded DNA virus with a genome size of about 5596 bp (see Wang et al., 2008). The B19 genome encodes three major proteins (see Ozawa and

Young, 1987): two viral capsid (see Heegaard and Brown, 2002; Wang et al., 2008) proteins (VP1 and VP2) and one non-structural protein 1 (NS1). NS1 plays a major role in the viral life cycle (see Raab et al., 2002). B19 may cause a number of generally self-limiting diseases. However, B19 DNA (see Conteville et al., 2015) has been detected in multiple tissues, including thyroid, bone marrow, brain, heart, kidneys, liver, lungs, lymphoid, skin, synovium, colon, testis, and tonsil. However, little or none information is available about the causal relationship between B19 and thyroid cancer.

2. Material and methods

Enders et al. provided data about age-specific IgG-positivity rate of human parvovirus B19 in children. “In children, the age-specific IgG-positivity rate increased from 12.2% (66/541) at 2 years of age to 71.9% (396/551) in those older than 10 years.” (see Enders et al., 2007) These data can be used to construct an appropriate fictive control group.

2.1. Data

2.1.1. Literature search

A search for relevant studies has been performed until October 22, 2021 using the electronic database PubMed with the following keywords used not individually but in combination: “parvovirus B19” and “thyroid cancer”. Reporting follows in adherence to Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (see Moher et al., 2009; Liberati et al., 2009).

Table 1. *Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis*

Identification:	PubMed	11
Screening:	Articles excluded I	4
Eligibility:	Articles eligible for analysis	7
	Articles excluded II	4
Inclusion:	Studies included (meta-analysis)	3

2.1.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Studies in English language which investigated the relationship between parvovirus B19 and thyroid cancer were considered. Studies with financial data access barriers were not considered. Reviews, case reports, letters, conference abstracts, or expert opinions were excluded and not considered.

2.1.3. Study selection and characteristics

The literature search yielded 11 potentially eligible titles. The abstracts were reviewed, inappropriate articles were excluded and removed. At the end, 3 articles which met the inclusion criteria and

were eligible for meta-analyses.

2.1.4. Data extraction and assessment of study quality

The data from articles which met which the inclusion and exclusion criteria were extracted and statistically analysed.

2.1.5. Study design and quality of data

The quality of the data(see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) of each study included was assessed separately by the index of unfairness or the index of independence. A study design should be fair and rOPresentative as much as possible in order to assured data, which can be worked with. The index of unfairness(see [Barukčić, 2019a](#)) and the index of independence(see [Barukčić, 2019b](#)) are indicating to which extent data could be biased. Under ideal conditions, it is desirable that $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$ or $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$ or that even $p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI}) = 0$.

Table 2. The quality of data (see [Barukčić, 2019a](#), p. 25)

p(IOU)	Quality of study design
$0 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,25$	Unfair study design
$0,25 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,5$	Very unfair study design
$0,5 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 0,75$	Highly unfair study design
$0,75 < p(\text{IOU}) \leq 1,0$	Extremely unfair study design

2.1.6. The study of Wang et al. (unfair)

Wang et al. (see [Wang et al., 2008](#)) evaluated whether parvovirus B19 is involved in thyroid carcinoma (TC). Normal and controls were examined for B19 DNA and capsid protein by immunohistochemistry (see [Coons et al., 1941](#)) or IHC, nested polymerase chain (see [Kleppe et al., 1971](#); [Mullis et al., 1986](#)) reaction (PCR) and in situ (see [Egger et al., 1994](#)) hybridization (ISH). The data and the statistical analysis is presented by table 3.

Table 3. B19 DNA(PCR) and Thyroid cancer (Study of Wang et al., 2008).

		Thyroid cancer		
		YES	NO	
B19 DNA(PCR)	YES	37	7	44
	NO	1	9	10
		38	16	54

Statistical analysis.

Causal relationship $k = 0,6302886291$

p Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,0000185004

p (SINE) = 0,9814814815

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,0263

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 0,1000

p Value (SINE) = 0,0183481043

p (IMP) = 0,8703703704

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 1,1136

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 3,0625

p Value (IMP) = 0,1215792883

p (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,8518518519

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₁ = 1,2136

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₂ = 3,0888

p Value (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,1377

p (EXCL) = 0,3148148148

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) = 31,1136

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) = 36,0263

p Value (EXCL) = 0,4960031118

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) = 8,4091

RR (sc) = 2,2256

Additional measures.

OR = 0,8519

IOR = 0,1950

Study design.

p(IOI) = 0,1111111111

p(IOUS) = 0,518518519

2.1.7. The study of Wang et al. (fair)

The data of Wang et al. (see [Wang et al., 2008](#)) have been highly unfair ($p(\text{IOU})=0,518518519$). Under the assumption of fair study design, we obtain the following picture. As a control group we used 41 children up to an age of 2 years, free of thyroid cancer. It is estimated that about 4/41 were B19 positive (see [Enders et al., 2007](#)).

Table 4. B19 DNA(PCR) and Thyroid cancer (Study Wang et al. (fair study design), 2008).

		Thyroid cancer		
		YES	NO	
B19 DNA(PCR)	YES	37	4	41
	NO	1	37	38
		38	41	79

Statistical analysis.

Causal relationship $k = 0,8761232349$

p Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,0000000000

p (SINE) = 0,9873417722

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,0263

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 0,0263

p Value (SINE) = 0,0125784495

p (IMP) = 0,9493670886

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 0,3902

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 0,3902

p Value (IMP) = 0,0493724290

p (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,9367088608

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₁ = 0,4166

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₂ = 0,4166

p Value (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,0613

p (EXCL) = 0,5316455696

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) = 33,3902

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) = 36,0263

p Value (EXCL) = 0,3739684003

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) = 34,2927

RR (sc) = 9,9803

Additional measures.

OR = 0,9367

IOR = 0,8761

Study design.

p(IOI) = 0,037974684

p(IOU) = 0

2.1.8. The study of Adamson et al., 2011 (fictive control group)

Adamson et al. (see [Adamson et al., 2011](#)) have not provided an appropriate control group. Under the assumption of a fair study design, we obtain constructed a **fictive control group**. As a control group we used 22 children up to an age of 2 years, free of thyroid cancer. It is estimated that about 2/22 children were B19 positive (see [Enders et al., 2007](#)).

Table 5. B19 DNA(IHC) and Thyroid cancer (Study of Adamson et al., 2011).

		Thyroid cancer		
		YES	NO	
B19 DNA(IHC)	YES	21	2	23
	NO	3	20	23
		24	22	46

Statistical analysis.

Causal relationship $k = 0,7833494518$

p Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,0000000575

p (SINE) = 0,9347826087

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,3750

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 0,3913

p Value (SINE) = 0,0631362248

p (IMP) = 0,9565217391

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 0,1739

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 0,1818

p Value (IMP) = 0,0425466319

p (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,8913043478

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₁ = 0,5652

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₂ = 0,5568

p (EXCL) = 0,5434782609

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) = 19,1739

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) = 18,3750

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) = 7,0000

RR (sc) = 9,6250

Additional measures.

OR = 0,8913

IOR = 0,7500

Study design.

p(IOI) = 0,02173913

p(IOUS) = 0,02173913

2.1.9. The study of Etemadi et al., 2017

Etemadi et al. (see [Etemadi et al., 2017](#)) investigated the presence of B19 in 36 paraffin-embedded thyroid specimens and its possible impact on thyroid cancer progression. Serum from 12 patients were used as control. The data of Etemadi et al. (see [Etemadi et al., 2017](#)) are shown by table 6. As can be seen, the study design has been very unfair ($p(\text{IOU})=0,458333333$).

Table 6. B19 DNA(PCR) and Thyroid cancer (The study of Etemadi et al.,2017).

		Thyroid cancer		
		YES	NO	
B19 DNA(PCR)	YES	31	3	34
	NO	5	9	14
		36	12	48

Statistical analysis.

Causal relationship $k = 0,5821817364$

p Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,0001801961

p (SINE) = 0,8958333333

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,6944

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 1,7857

p (IMP) = 0,9375000000

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 0,2647

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 0,7500

p (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,8333333333

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₁ = 2,0504

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₂ = 1,4444

p (EXCL) = 0,3541666667

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) = 28,2647

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) = 26,6944

Relative risk (RR).

RR (nc) = 2,5529

RR (sc) = 3,4444

Additional measures.

OR = 0,8333

IOR = 0,2157

Study design.

p(IOI) = 0,041666667

p(IOU) = 0,4583333333

2.1.10. The study of Etemadi et al., 2017 (fair study design)

Table 7. B19 DNA(PCR) and Thyroid cancer (The study of Etemadi et al., 2017).

		Thyroid cancer		
		YES	NO	
B19 DNA(PCR)	YES	31	3	34
	NO	5	31	36
		36	34	70

Statistical analysis.Causal relationship $k = 0,7728758170$

p Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,0000000000

p (SINE) = 0,9285714286 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,6944 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 0,6944**p (IMP) = 0,9571428571** $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 0,2647 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 0,2647**p (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,8857142857** $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₁ = 0,9592 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₂ = 0,9592**p (EXCL) = 0,5571428571** $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) = 28,2647 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) = 26,6944**Relative risk (RR).**

RR (nc) = 6,5647

RR (sc) = 9,7593

Additional measures.

OR = 0,8857

IOR = 0,7729

Study design.

p(IOI) = 0,028571429

p(IOU) = 0

2.1.11. The study of Etemadi et al. (B19 IgG)

Table 8. B19 IgG and thyroid cancer (The study of Etemadi et al., 2017).

		Thyroid cancer		
		YES	NO	
B19 IgG	YES	35	10	45
	NO	1	2	3
		36	12	48

Statistical analysis.Causal relationship $k = 0,2484519975$

p Value right tailed (HGD) = 0,1500925069

p (SINE) = 0,9791666667 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,0278 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 0,3333**p (IMP) = 0,7916666667** $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 2,2222 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 8,3333**p (SINE \cap IMP) = 0,7708333333** $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₁ = 2,5556 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE \cap IMP)₂ = 8,3611**p (EXCL) = 0,2708333333** $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) = 27,2222 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) = 34,0278**Relative risk (RR).**

RR (nc) = 2,3333

RR (sc) = 1,1667

Additional measures.

OR = 0,7708

IOR = 0,0370

Study design.

p(IOI)= 0,1875

p(IOU)= 0,6875

2.2. Methods

The nature of definitions is discussed by scientist since ancient times. Many times, several different kinds of definitions are necessary to solve a scientific issue properly. Even if often in play, inappropriate definitions can lead to logical fallacies too.

2.2.1. The number +0

Definition 2.1 (The number +0). Let i denote the imaginary number (see [Bombelli, 1579](#)). The imaginary number i is known to be defined solely by the property that its square is -1 . According to today valid rules of algebra, the number +0 is defined as the expression

$$+0 \equiv +1 \times +0 \equiv +0 \times +1 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv +1 + i^2 \equiv +1 + e^{i\pi} \equiv \neg(+1) \quad (2.1)$$

while '=' or \equiv denotes the equals sign (see [Recorde, 1557](#)) or equality sign (see [Rolle, 1690](#)) used to indicate equality and '-' (see [Widmann, 1489](#); [Pacioli, 1494](#)) denotes minus signs used to rOPResent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus (see [Recorde, 1557](#)) signs used to rOPResent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well. Negation is denoted by \neg .

Remark 2.1. Roger Cotes (1682 – 1716) (see [Cotes and Halley, 1714](#)) or Leonhard Euler's (1707 – 1783) identity (see [Euler, 1748](#)) is regarded as one of the most beautiful equations (see [Wilson, 2018](#)). In this context, it is provisionally presumed, that Euler's identity (see [Euler, 1748](#)) is logically sound and correct.

2.2.2. The number +1

Definition 2.2 (The number +1). According to today valid rules of algebra, the number +1 is defined as the expression

$$+1 \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \equiv \neg(+0) \quad (2.2)$$

while again '=' or \equiv may denote the equals sign (see [Recorde, 1557](#)) or equality sign (see [Rolle, 1690](#)) used to indicate equality and '-' (see [Widmann, 1489](#); [Pacioli, 1494](#)) denotes minus signs used to rOPResent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus (see [Recorde, 1557](#)) signs used to rOPResent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

2.2.3. Single event distribution

Let a **random variable** (see [Gosset, 1914](#)) X denote something like a function defined on a probability space, which itself maps from the sample space (see [Neyman and Pearson, 1933](#)) to the real numbers. A single event distribution is more or less a discrete probability distribution of any random variable X which takes a certain (observer independent) single value X_t at a **Bernoulli trial** (see [Us-pensky, 1937](#), p. 45) (period of time) t with the probability $p(X_t)$. The same random variable X takes a certain single anti value \underline{X}_t at a Bernoulli trial (period of time) t with the probability $1-p(X_t)$. There are conditions in nature where a random variable X can take only the values either +0 or +1. Under these conditions the random variable X takes the value 1 with probability $p(X_t = +1)$ and the value 0 with probability $q(X_t = +0) = 1 - p(X_t = +1)$ while the single event distribution passes over into the **Bernoulli distribution**, named after Swiss mathematician Jacob Bernoulli (see [Bernoulli, 1713](#)). Less formally, many times, the Bernoulli distribution is rOPResented by a (possibly not biased) coin toss where 1 and 0 would rOPResent 'heads' and 'tails' (or vice versa), respectively. However, the relationship between random variables (see [Gosset, 1914](#)) can be investigated by many (see [Gosset, 1908](#)) methods, including the tools of probability theory, too.

Definition 2.3 (Two by two table of single event random variables).

The two by two or contingency table which has been introduced by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1904](#)) in 1904 harbours still a large variety of topics and debates. Central to this is the problem to apply the laws of classical logic on data sets, which concerns the justification of inferences which extrapolate from sample data to general facts. Nevertheless, a contingency table is still an appropriate theoretical model too for studying the relationships between random variables, including *Bernoulli* (see [Bernoulli, 1713](#)) (i.e. +0/+1) distributed random variables existing or occurring at the same *Bernoulli trial* (see [Uspensky, 1937](#)) (period of time) t .

In this context, let a random variable A at the *Bernoulli trial* (see [Uspensky, 1937](#)) (period of time) t , denoted by A_t , indicate a risk factor, a condition, a cause et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(A_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (see [Uspensky, 1937](#)) (period of time) t . Let $E(A_t)$ denote the expectation value of A_t . In general it is

$$p(A_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \quad (2.3)$$

The expectation value $E(A_t)$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv A_t \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t)) \\ &\equiv (A_t \times p(a_t)) + (A_t \times p(b_t)) \\ &\equiv E(a_t) + E(b_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(A_t) &\equiv A_t \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(A_t) \\ &\equiv p(A_t) \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{A}_t) \equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \quad (2.6)$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{A}_t)$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned} E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv A_t \times (p(c_t) + p(d_t)) \\ &\equiv (A_t \times p(c_t)) + (A_t \times p(d_t)) \\ &\equiv E(c_t) + E(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} E(\underline{A}_t) &\equiv A_t \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv (1 - p(A_t)) \\ &\equiv p(c_t) + p(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

Let a random variable B at the *Bernoulli trial* (see [Uspensky, 1937](#)) (period of time) t , denoted by B_t , indicate an outcome, a conditioned, an effect et cetera and occur or exist with the probability $p(B_t)$ at the *Bernoulli trial* (see [Uspensky, 1937](#)) (period of time) t . Let $E(B_t)$ denote the expectation value of B_t . In general it is

$$p(B_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \quad (2.9)$$

The expectation value $E(B_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned} E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv B_t \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t)) \\ &\equiv (B_t \times p(a_t)) + (B_t \times p(c_t)) \\ &\equiv E(a_t) + E(c_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(B_t) &\equiv B_t \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times p(B_t) \\ &\equiv p(B_t) \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$p(\underline{B}_t) \equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t) \equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \quad (2.12)$$

The expectation value $E(\underline{B}_t)$ is given by the equation

$$\begin{aligned} E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv \underline{B}_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv \underline{B}_t \times (p(b_t) + p(d_t)) \\ &\equiv (\underline{B}_t \times p(b_t)) + (\underline{B}_t \times p(d_t)) \\ &\equiv E(b_t) + E(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(\underline{B}_t) &\equiv \underline{B}_t \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv (+0 + 1) \times (1 - p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv (1 - p(B_t)) \\ &\equiv p(b_t) + p(d_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

Let $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned} E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\ &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\ &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(a_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(a_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(a_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.16}$$

Let $p(b_t) = p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.17}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(b_t) &\equiv E(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.18}$$

Let $p(c_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \times p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.19}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(c_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(c_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.20}$$

Let $p(d_t) = p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t)$ denote the joint probability distribution of not A_t and not B_t at the same Bernoulli trial (period of time) t . In general, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.21}$$

Under conditions of +0/+1 distributed Bernoulli random variables, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(d_t) &\equiv E(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv (\neg A_t \times \neg B_t) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv ((+0 + 1) \times (+0 + 1)) \times p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(\neg A_t \wedge \neg B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(d_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.22}$$

In general, it is

$$p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \equiv +1 \tag{2.23}$$

Table 9 provide us with an overview of the definitions above.

Table 9. The two by two table of Bernoulli random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

2.2.4. Binomial random variables

Definition 2.4 (Two by two table of Binomial random variables).

Under conditions where *the probability of an event, an outcome, a success et cetera is constant from Bernoulli trial to Bernoulli trial t* , it is

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= N \times E(A_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (A_t \times p(A_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(A_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.24}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 B &= N \times E(B_t) \\
 &\equiv N \times (B_t \times p(B_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times (p(A_t) + p(c_t)) \\
 &\equiv N \times p(B_t)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.25}$$

where N denotes the population size. Furthermore, it is

$$a \equiv N \times (E(A_t)) \equiv N \times (p(A_t)) \tag{2.26}$$

and

$$b \equiv N \times (E(B_t)) \equiv N \times (p(B_t)) \quad (2.27)$$

and

$$c \equiv N \times (E(c_t)) \equiv N \times (p(c_t)) \quad (2.28)$$

and

$$d \equiv N \times (E(d_t)) \equiv N \times (p(d_t)) \quad (2.29)$$

and

$$a + b + c + d \equiv A + \underline{A} \equiv B + \underline{B} \equiv N \quad (2.30)$$

Table 10 provide us again an overview of a two by two table of Binomial random variables.

Table 10. The two by two table of Binomial random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	d
		B	\underline{B}	N

2.2.5. Independence

Definition 2.5 (Independence).

In general, an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t need not but can be independent of the existence or of the occurrence of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t . Mathematically, independence (see [Moivre, 1718](#); [Kolmogoroff, 1933](#)) in terms of probability theory is defined at the same (period of) time t (i.e. Bernoulli trial t) as

$$p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv p(A_t) \times p(B_t)$$

$$\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \wedge B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t))}{N} \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \quad (2.31)$$

2.2.6. Dependence

Definition 2.6 (Dependence).

The dependence of events (see [Barukčić, 1989](#), p. 57-61) is defined as

$$p\left(\underbrace{A_t \wedge B_t \wedge C_t \wedge \dots}_n\right) \equiv \sqrt[n]{\underbrace{p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \times p(C_t) \times \dots}_n} \quad (2.32)$$

2.2.7. Exclusion relationship

Definition 2.7 (Exclusion relationship [EXCL]).

Mathematically, the exclusion (EXCL) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t | B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (see Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{b + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.33}$$

Based on the 1913 Henry Maurice Sheffer (1882-1964) relationship, the Sheffer stroke (see Sheffer, 1913; Nicod, 1917) usually denoted by \uparrow , it is $p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t)$ (see table 11).

Table 11. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine) A_t	TRUE	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.2. Pfizer Inc. and BioNTech SE announced on Monday, November 09, 2020 - 06:45am results from a Phase 3 COVID-19 vaccine trial with 43,538 participants which provides evidence that their vaccine (BNT162b2) is preventing COVID-19 in participants without evidence of prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. In toto, 170 confirmed cases of COVID-19 were evaluated, with 8 in the vaccine group versus 162 in the placebo group. The exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{Vaccine : BNT162b2} | \text{COVID-19(infection)}) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(a_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - \left(\frac{8}{43538} \right) \\
 &\equiv +0,99981625
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.34}$$

with a P Value = 0,000184.

2.2.8. The goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.8 (The χ^2 goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about an exclusion relationship $p(A_t | B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c + d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A}\end{aligned}\quad (2.35)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B}\end{aligned}\quad (2.36)$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of an exclusion relationship/distribution $p(A_t | B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis has to be accepted. Yate's (see [Yates, 1934](#)) continuity correction was not used under these circumstances.

2.2.9. The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.9 (The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship).

It is known that as a sample size, N , increases, a sampling distribution of a special test statistic approaches the normal distribution (central limit theorem). Under these circumstances, the left-tailed (lt) p Value (see [Barukčić, 2019c](#)) of an exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t | B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t|B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(a/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (2.37)$$

A low p-value may provide some evidence of statistical significance.

2.2.10. Neither nor conditions

Definition 2.10 (Neither A_t nor B_t conditions [NOR]).

Mathematically, a neither A_t nor B_t condition (or rejection according to the French philosopher and logician Jean George Pierre Nicod (1893-1924), i.e. Jean Nicod's statement (see [Nicod, 1924](#))) relationship (NOR), denoted by $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (see [Barukčić, 1989](#), p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N - \sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \wedge B_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{N \times (p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.38}$$

2.2.11. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a neither nor condition relationship

Definition 2.11 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

A neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship $p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution). The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 may be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.39}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t \downarrow B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} + \\
 &\quad \frac{((a + c) - B)^2}{B} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}} + 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.40}$$

Yate's (see [Yates, 1934](#)) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.12. The left-tailed p Value of a neither nor B condition relationship

Definition 2.12 (The left-tailed p Value of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (see [Barukčić, 2019c](#)) of a neither A_t nor B_t condition relationship can

be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{lt}(A_t \downarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \downarrow B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-p(A_t \vee B_t)} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+b+c)/N)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.41}$$

where \vee may denote disjunction or logical inclusive or. In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. In general, it is $p(A_t \vee B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see table 12).

Table 12. Neither A_t nor B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	0	0
	NO	0	1	1
		0	1	1

2.2.13. Necessary condition

Definition 2.13 (Necessary condition [*Conditio sine qua non*]).

Mathematically, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (see Barukčić, 1989, p. 15-28) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.42}$$

It is $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \downarrow B_t)$ (see Table 13).

Table 13. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	+0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.3. A necessary condition A_t is characterized itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (see Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 2020b,c,d). **Example.** A human being cannot live without water. A human being cannot live without gaseous oxygen et cetera. Water itself is a necessary condition of human life. However, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life too. Thus far, even if water is given and even if water is a necessary condition of human life, without gaseous oxygen there will be no human life. In general, if a conditioned or an outcome B_t depends on the necessary condition A_t and equally on numerous other necessary conditions, an event B_t will not occur if A_t itself is not given independently of the occurrence of other necessary conditions.

2.2.14. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

Definition 2.14 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, hypothesis about the conditio sine qua non relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution), first described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see Helmert, 1876) and later rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see Pearson, 1900) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio sine qua non relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B}\end{aligned}\tag{2.43}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{A} + \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{A}\end{aligned}\tag{2.44}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . It has not yet been finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (see Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.2.15. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship

Definition 2.15 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (see Barukčić, 2019c) of the conditio sine qua non relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.45)$$

2.2.16. Sufficient condition

Definition 2.16 (Sufficient condition [Conditio per quam]).

Mathematically, the sufficient condition (IMP) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (see Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t)}{N \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + c + d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.46)$$

It is $p(A_t > -B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ (see Table 14).

Table 14. Sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p(A_t)$
	A_t	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Remark 2.4. A sufficient condition A_t is characterized by the property that another event B_t will occur if A_t is given, if A_t itself occurred (see Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a,b, 2020a; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 2020b,c,d). **Example.** The ground, the streets, the trees, human beings and many other objects too will become wet during a heavy rain. Especially, **if** it is raining (event A_t), **then** human beings will be wet (event B_t). However, even if this is a common human wisdom, a human being equipped with an appropriate umbrella (denoted by R_t) need not to become wet even during a heavy rain. An appropriate umbrella (R_t) is similar to an event which can counteract the occurrence of

another event (B_t) and can be understood something as an anti-dot of another event. In other words, an appropriate umbrella is an antidote of the effect of rain on human body, an appropriate umbrella has the potential to protect humans from the effect of rain on their body. It is a good rule of thumb that the following relationship

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) + p(R_t \wedge B_t) \equiv +1 \quad (2.47)$$

indicates that R_t is an antidote of A_t . However, taking a shower, swimming in a lake et cetera may make human hair wet too. More than anything else, however, these events does not affect the final outcome, the effect of raining on human body.

2.2.17. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.17 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about the conditio per quam relationship $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio per quam relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c+d) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} \end{aligned} \quad (2.48)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b+d))^2}{B} + \frac{((a+c) - B)^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} \end{aligned} \quad (2.49)$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of the conditio per quam relationship/distribution $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis is accepted. Yate's (see [Yates, 1934](#)) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.18. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship

Definition 2.18 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (see [Barukčić, 2019c](#)) of the conditio per quam relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \rightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(b/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.50)$$

Again, a low p-value indicates a statistical significance.

2.2.19. Necessary and sufficient conditions

Definition 2.19 (Necessary and sufficient conditions [EQV]).

The necessary and sufficient condition (EQV) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined(see [Barukčić, 1989](#), p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \vee B_t) \wedge (\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv p(a_t) + p(d_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{a + d}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.51)$$

2.2.20. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.20 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

Even the necessary and sufficient condition relationship $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + b))^2}{A} + \\ &\quad \frac{d - ((c + d))^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + \frac{c^2}{A} \end{aligned} \quad (2.52)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{d - ((b + d))^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + \frac{b^2}{B}\end{aligned}\quad (2.53)$$

The calculated $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . Under conditions where the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship/distribution $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$, the $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero. It is to be cleared whether Yate's (see [Yates, 1934](#)) continuity correction should be used at all.

2.2.21. The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.21 (The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (see [Barukčić, 2019c](#)) of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((b+c)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (2.54)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance. Table 15 may provide an overview of the theoretical distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

Table 15. Necessary and sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	1	0	1
	NO	0	1	1
		1	1	2

2.2.22. Either or conditions

Definition 2.22 (Either A_t or B_t conditions [NEQV]).

Mathematically, an either A_t or B_t condition relationship (NEQV), denoted by $p(A_t >-< B_t)$ in terms

of statistics and probability theory, is defined (see Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t > - < B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \wedge \underline{B}_t) \vee (\underline{A}_t \wedge B_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + c}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.55}$$

It is $p(A_t > - < B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t < - > B_t)$ (see Table 16).

Table 16. Either A_t or B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	1	1
	NO	1	0	1
		1	1	2

2.2.23. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.23 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship).

An either or condition relationship $p(A_t > - < B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t > - < B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{c - ((c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.56}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t > - < B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{b - ((b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + \frac{d^2}{\underline{B}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.57}$$

Yate's (see [Yates, 1934](#)) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.2.24. The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.24 (The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (see [Barukčić, 2019c](#)) of an either or condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} pValue_{lt}(A_t > - < B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t > - < B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+d)/N)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.58)$$

In this context, a low p-value indicates again a statistical significance.

2.2.25. Causal relationship k

Definition 2.25 (Causal relationship k).

Nonetheless, mathematically, the causal (see [Barukčić, 2011a,b, 2012](#)) relationship (see [Barukčić, 1989, 1997, 2005, 2016, 2017a](#)) between a cause U_t (German: Ursache) and an effect W_t (German: Wirkung), denoted by $k(U_t, W_t)$, is defined *at each single Bernoulli trial t* in terms of statistics and probability theory as

$$\begin{aligned} k(U_t, W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(U_t, W_t)}{\sigma(U_t) \times \sigma(W_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(U_t \wedge W_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t))) \times (p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t)))}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.59)$$

where $\sigma(U_t, W_t)$ denotes the co-variance between a cause U_t and an effect W_t *at every single Bernoulli trial t*, $\sigma(U_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of a cause U_t at the same single Bernoulli trial t, $\sigma(W_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of an effect W_t at same single Bernoulli trial t. Table 17 illustrates the theoretically possible relationships between a cause and an effect.

Table 17. Sample space and the causal relationship k

		Effect B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

2.2.26. Cause and effect

Definition 2.26 (Cause and effect).

Table 18. What is the cause, what is the effect?

		Effect W_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause	TRUE	+1	+0	$p(U_t)$
U_t	FALSE	+0	+1	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

What is the cause, what is the effect? Under conditions of a **positive** causal relationship k , an event U_t which is for sure a cause of another event W_t is at the same time t a necessary and sufficient condition of an event W_t . Table 18 may illustrate this relationship.

The collapse and the logical inconsistency of the risk ratio under these circumstances is obvious.

As can be seen, there is a kind of strange mirroring between U_t and W_t . Lastly, both are converses of each other too. In other words, U_t 's being a necessary condition of W_t 's is equivalent to W_t 's being a sufficient condition of U_t 's (and vice versa). In general, it is

$$(U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \equiv (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t) \equiv ((U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t)) \equiv +1 \quad (2.60)$$

In our everyday words,

without

U_t

no

W_t

is equivalent with

if

W_t

then

U_t

and vice versa.

Necessary and sufficient conditions are relationships used to describe the relationship between two events at the same Bernoulli trial t . In more detail, if U_t then W_t is equivalent with W_t is necessary for U_t , because the truth of U_t guarantees the truth of W_t . In general, it is

$$(\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \equiv (W_t \vee \underline{U}_t) \equiv ((\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \wedge (W_t \vee \underline{U}_t)) \equiv +1 \quad (2.61)$$

In other words, it is impossible to have U_t without W_t (see Bloch, 2011). Similarly, U_t is sufficient for W_t , because U_t being true always implies that W_t is true, but U_t not being true does not always imply that W_t is not true.

For instance, **without** gaseous oxygen (U_t), there would be **no** burning wax candle (W_t); hence the relationship **if** burning wax candle (W_t) **then** gaseous oxygen (U_t) is equally true and given.

This simple example may illustrate the reason why a sufficient condition alone is not enough to describe a cause completely. The relationship **if** burning wax candle (W_t) **then** gaseous oxygen (U_t) is given. Independently of this fact, a burning wax candle is not the cause of gaseous oxygen. Therefore,

in order to be a cause of oxygen, additional evidence is necessary that a burning wax candle is a necessary condition of gaseous oxygen too. However, even if the relationship **without** gaseous oxygen **no** burning wax candle is given, this relationship is not given vice versa. The relationship **without** burning wax candle **no** gaseous oxygen is not given. Like other fundamental concepts, the concepts of cause and effect can be associated with difficulties too. In order to recognise a causal relationship between U_t and W_t , it is necessary that the same study or that at least different studies provide evidence of a necessary condition between U_t and W_t and of a sufficient condition between U_t and W_t and if possible of a **necessary and sufficient condition** between U_t and W_t too.

Mathematically, a necessary and sufficient condition between U_t and W_t is defined as

$$(U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \equiv +1 \quad (2.62)$$

However, I think it necessary to make a clear distinction between a necessary and sufficient condition and the converse relationship (Eq. 2.60) above.

$$((U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{W}_t \vee U_t)) \neq (U_t \vee \underline{W}_t) \wedge (\underline{U}_t \vee W_t) \quad (2.63)$$

2.2.27. Study design and bias

Systematic observation and experimentation, inductive and deductive reasoning are essential for any formation and testing of hypotheses and theories about the natural world. In one way or another, logically and mathematically sound scientific methods and concepts are crucial constituents of any scientific progress. When all goes well, different scientists at different times and places using the same scientific methodology should be able to generate the same scientific knowledge. However, more than half (52%) of scientists surveyed believe that studies do not successfully reproduce sufficiently similar or the same results as the original studies (see Baker, 2016). In a very large study on publication bias in meta-analyses, Kicinski et al. (see Kicinski et al., 2015) found evidence of publication bias even in systematic reviews. Therefore, a careful re-evaluation of the study/experimental design, the statistical methods and other scientific means which underpin scientific inquiry and research goals appears to be necessary once and again. While it is important to recognise the shortcoming of today's science, one issue which has shaped debates over studies published is the question: **has a study really measured what it set out to?** Even if studies carried out can vary greatly in detail, the data from the studies itself provide information about the credibility of the data.

Index of unfairness (IOU)

Definition 2.27 (Index of unfairness).

The index of unfairness (see Barukčić, 2019d) (IOU) is defined as

$$p(\text{IOU}(A, B)) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{n} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (2.64)$$

A very good study design should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$. In point of fact, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOU})$, a $p(\text{IOU})$ up to 0.25 could be of use too. An index of unfairness is of use to prove whether sample data are biased and whether sample data can be used for Chi-square based analysis of necessary conditions, of sufficient conditions and of causal relationships.

Index of independence (IOI)

Definition 2.28 (Index of independence).

The index of independence (see Barukčić, 2019e) (IOI) is defined as

$$p(\text{IOI}(A, \underline{B})) \equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{n} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (2.65)$$

A very good study design which aims to prove **an exclusion relationship or a causal relationship** should assure as much as possible a $p(\text{IOI}) = 0$. However, once again, against the background of lacking enough experience with the use of $p(\text{IOI})$, sample data with a $p(\text{IOI})$ up to 0.25 are of use too. Today, most double-blind placebo-controlled studies are based on the demand that **$p(\text{IOU}) = p(\text{IOI})$** while the value of $p(\text{IOU})$ has been widely neglected. Such an approach leads to unnecessary big sample sizes, the increase of cost, the waste of time and, most importantly of all, to epistemological systematically biased sample data and conclusions drawn. A change is necessary.

Index of relationship (IOR)

Definition 2.29 (Index of relationship (IOR)).

Due to several reasons, it is not always easy to identify the unique characteristics between two events like A_t and B_t . And more than that, it is difficult to decide what to do, and much more difficult to know in which direction one should think and which decision is right. Sometimes it is helpful to know at least something about the direction of the relationship between two events like A_t and B_t . Under conditions where $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$, the index of relationship (see Barukčić, 2021a), abbreviated as IOR, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{IOR}(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{p(A_t \wedge B_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(B_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \right) \\ &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times a}{A \times B} \right) - 1 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.66)$$

where $p(A_t)$ denotes the probability of an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t and $p(B_t)$ denotes the probability of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t while $p(a_t)$ denotes the joint probability of $p(A_t \text{ AND } B_t)$ at the same Bernoulli trial t and a , A and B may denote the expectation values.

Lemma 2.1 (THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELATIVE RISK (RR) AND INDEX OF RELATIONSHIP (IOR)). *The relationship between relative risk (RR_{nc}) and index of relationship (IOR) is determined by the equation*

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(\frac{(\text{Not}A_t) \times B_t}{N \times c_t} \right) \times (\text{IOR}(A_t, B_t) + 1) \quad (2.67)$$

Proof. The relative risk RR_{nc} is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{a_t \times (NotA_t)}{c_t \times A_t} \quad (2.68)$$

Rearranging, it is

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t)} \equiv a_t \quad (2.69)$$

Rearranging further, we obtain

$$\frac{N \times (RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t) \times A_t \times B_t} \equiv \frac{N \times a_t}{A_t \times B_t} \quad (2.70)$$

It follows that

$$\left(\frac{N \times (RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t) \times A_t \times B_t} \right) - 1 \equiv \left(\frac{N \times a_t}{A_t \times B_t} \right) - 1 \quad (2.71)$$

or that

$$\left(\frac{N \times (RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t) \times B_t \times A_t} \right) - 1 \equiv IOR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.72)$$

Rearranging equation before, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{N \times (RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t}{(NotA_t) \times B_t} \right) \equiv IOR(A_t, B_t) + 1 \quad (2.73)$$

In general, it is

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(\frac{(NotA_t) \times B_t}{N \times c_t} \right) \times (IOR(A_t, B_t) + 1) \quad (2.74)$$

□

2.2.28. Risk ratio (RR)

Relative risk (RR_{nc})

Definition 2.30 (Relative risk (RR_{nc})).

The degree of association between the two binomial variables can be assessed by a number of very different coefficients, the relative (see [Cornfield, 1951](#); [Sadovsky et al., 1953](#),) risk is one (see [Barukčić, 2021b](#)) of them. In general, relative risk RR_{nc} , which provides some evidence of a necessary condition, is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} = \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(c_t) \times p(A_t)} = \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotA_t)}{N \times p(c_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} = \frac{a_t \times (NotA_t)}{c_t \times A_t} = \frac{EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.75)$$

That what scientist generally understand by relative risk is the ratio of a probability of an event occurring with an exposure versus the probability of an event occurring without an exposure. In other words,

relative risk = (probability(event in exposed group)) / (probability(the same event in not exposed group)).

A $RR(A_t, B_t) = +1$ means that exposure does not affect the outcome or both are independent of each other while $RR(A_t, B_t)$ less than +1 means that the risk of the outcome is decreased by the exposure. In this context, an $RR(A_t, B_t)$ greater than +1 denotes that the risk of the outcome is increased by the exposure. Widely known problems with odds ratio and relative risk are already documented in literature.

Relative risk (RR (sc))

Definition 2.31 (Relative risk (RR (sc))).

The relative risk (sc), which provides some evidence of a sufficient condition, is calculated from the point of view of an outcome and is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} = \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)}}{\frac{p(b_t)}{p(NotB_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotB_t)}{p(b_t) \times p(B_t)} = \frac{N \times p(a_t) \times N \times p(NotB_t)}{N \times p(b_t) \times N \times p(B_t)} = \frac{a_t \times (NotB_t)}{b_t \times B_t} = \frac{OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.76)$$

Example.

Tugwell et al. (see [Tugwell et al., 2004](#)) investigated a chickenpox outbreak in an Oregon elementary school in October 2001. "Twenty-one cases occurred in 9 of 16 classrooms. In these 9 classrooms, 18 of 152 (12%) vaccinated students developed chickenpox, compared with 3 of 7 (43%) unvaccinated students." These data are illustrated by the following two by two table.

Table 19. Outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon in 2002

		Varicella B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Vaccinated A_t	TRUE	$a_t = 18$	$b_t = 134$	$A_t = 152$
	FALSE	$c_t = 3$	$d_t = 4$	$\underline{A}_t = 7$
		$B_t = 21$	$\underline{B}_t = 138$	$N_t = 159$

The risk ratio RR_{nc} is calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} &\equiv \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(NotA_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(NotA_t)}{p(A_t) \times p(c_t)} \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times \underline{A_t}}{c_t \times A_t} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{18 \times 7}{3 \times 152} \right) \\
 &\equiv \frac{0.118}{0.42} \\
 &\equiv 0.28
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.77}$$

The risk ratio is $RR_{nc} = +0.28$ and less than 1.0 which indicates that a vaccination has not been a necessary condition for the outbreak observed. Quite the opposite, a decreased risk or a protective effect for the children which were vaccinated (exposed to vaccine) is documented. However, the risk ratio of $RR_{nc} = +0.28$ is completely misleading in this context, as can be seen by table 20.

Table 20. Vaccinated and Chickenpox outbreak (Study of Tugwell et al., 2004).

		Chickenpox		
		YES	NO	
Vaccinated	YES	18	134	152
	NO	3	4	7
		21	138	159
Causal relationship k =		-0,1879290573		
p Value left tailed (HGD) =		0,0493451		
p (SINE) =		0,9811320755		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) =		0,4286		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) =		1,2857		
p Value (SINE) =		0,0186910395		
p (EXCL) =		0,8867924528		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — A_t) =		2,1316		
$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL — B_t) =		15,4286		
p Value (EXCL) =		0,1070346915		
OR =		0,1384		
RR (nc) =		0,2763		
RR (sc) =		0,8827		
IOR =		-0,1034		
p(IOI) =		0,823899371		
p(IOU) =		0,088050314		
Vaccine efficacy (%) =		72,3684		

The data as published by Tugwell et al. (see [Tugwell et al., 2004](#)) are self-contradictory. There is some evidence that the vaccination itself has not been responsible for the outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon (USA) in 2002 ($k < +0$; p Value left tailed (HGD)=0,0493451). However, the exclusion relationship is $p(\text{EXCL})=0,8867924528$ and not significant. Nonetheless, the data presented does not support the conclusion that the vaccination prevents from the outbreak of varicella (chickenpox). The index of independence ($p(\text{IOI})$) is $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,823899371$. In other words, the study design of the study of Tugwell et al. (see [Tugwell et al., 2004](#)) has been extremely unfair in this respect. Altogether, it cannot be excluded that the data are potentially biased.

The question is justified, has the vaccination against varicella (chickenpox) been responsible for the outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon (USA) in 2002? Taking the data as published by Tugwell et al. (see [Tugwell et al., 2004](#)) for granted, we need to conclude the following: yes!

Without vaccination against varicella (chickenpox) in an Oregon elementary school in 2001 **no** outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,9811$; p Value (SINE) = 0,0187; $p(\text{IOU})= 0,0881$ et cetera).

However, is such a conclusion ([Barukčić, 2021c](#)) really inevitable, completely justified and free of any errors?

The study design is acceptable ($p(\text{IOU})= 0,0881$) and indicates that the data presented are of use for the analysis of a *conditio sine qua non* relationship. However, a negative causal relationship k ($k = -0,1879$), even if $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,0881$ is very impressive, does not support the hypothesis of necessary condition at all. In other words, the data as presented by Tugwell et al. (see [Tugwell et al., 2004](#)) are self-contradictory and we cannot draw any valuable conclusion out of the same. Unfortunately, the close connection between vaccination and outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon in 2002 is rather masked than discovered by the risk ratio. Even though it is considered highly desirable, the conclusion that the vaccination protected against an outbreak of varicella (chickenpox) in Oregon (USA) in 2002 is not justified for sure due to the data published.

Relative risk reduction (RRR)

Definition 2.32 (Relative risk reduction (RRR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RRR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.78)$$

Vaccine efficacy (VE)

Definition 2.33 (Vaccine efficacy (VE)).

Vaccine efficacy is defined as the percentage reduction of a disease in a vaccinated group of people as compared to an unvaccinated group of people.

$$\begin{aligned} VE(A_t, B_t) &\equiv 100 \times (1 - RR(A_t, B_t)) \\ &\equiv 100 \times \left(\frac{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)}{CER(A_t, B_t)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.79)$$

Historically, vaccine efficacy has been designed to evaluate the efficacy of a certain vaccine by Greenwood and Yule

in 1915 for the cholera and typhoid vaccines (Greenwood and Yule, 1915) and best measured using double-blind, randomized, clinical controlled trials. However, the calculated vaccine efficacy is depending too much on the study design, can lead to erroneous conclusions and is only of very limited value.

Experimental event rate (EER)

Definition 2.34 (Experimental event rate (EER)).

$$EER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \quad (2.80)$$

Definition 2.35 (Control event rate (CER)).

$$CER(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(A_t)} = \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} \quad (2.81)$$

Absolute risk reduction (ARR)

Definition 2.36 (Absolute risk reduction (ARR)).

$$\begin{aligned} ARR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(c_t)}{p(A_t)} - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \\ &= \frac{c_t}{c_t + d_t} - \frac{a_t}{a_t + b_t} \\ &= CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.82)$$

Absolute risk increase (ARI)

Definition 2.37 (Absolute risk increase (ARI)).

$$\begin{aligned} ARI(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(A_t)} \\ &= EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.83)$$

Number needed to treat (NNT)

Definition 2.38 (Number needed to treat (NNT)).

$$NNT(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CER(A_t, B_t) - EER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.84)$$

An ideal number needed to treat (see [Laupacis et al., 1988](#); [Cook and Sackett, 1995](#)), mathematically the reciprocal of the absolute risk reduction, is $NNT = 1$. Under these circumstances, everyone improves with a treatment, while no one improves with control. A higher number needed to treat indicates more or less a treatment which is less effective.

Number needed to harm (NNH)

Definition 2.39 (Number needed to harm (NNH)).

$$NNH(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{EER(A_t, B_t) - CER(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.85)$$

The number needed to harm (see [Massel and Cruickshank, 2002](#)), mathematically the inverse of the absolute risk increase, indicates at the end how many patients need to be exposed to a certain factor, in order to observe a harm in one patient that would not otherwise have been harmed.

Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)

Definition 2.40 (Outcome prevalence rate (OPR)).

$$OPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)} = \frac{a_t}{a_t + c_t} \quad (2.86)$$

Control prevalence rate (CPR)

Definition 2.41 (Control prevalence rate (CPR)).

$$CPR(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{p(b_t)}{p(B_t)} = \frac{b_t}{b_t + d_t} \quad (2.87)$$

Bias and confounding is present to some degree in all research. In order to assess the relationship of exposure with a disease or an outcome, a fictive control group (i.e. of newborn or of young children et cetera) can be of use too. Under certain circumstances, even a $CPR = 0$ is imaginable.

Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)

Definition 2.42 (Absolute prevalence reduction (APR)).

$$APR(A_t, B_t) \equiv CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.88)$$

Absolute prevalence increase (API)

Definition 2.43 (Absolute prevalence increase (API)).

$$API(A_t, B_t) \equiv OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.89)$$

Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)

Definition 2.44 (Relative prevalence reduction (RPR)).

$$\begin{aligned} RPR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \frac{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)}{CPR(A_t, B_t)} \\ &= 1 - RR(A_t, B_t)_{sc} \end{aligned} \quad (2.90)$$

The index NNS

Definition 2.45 (The index NNS).

$$NNS(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{CPR(A_t, B_t) - OPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.91)$$

Mathematically, the index NNS is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence reduction.

The index NNI

Definition 2.46 (The index NNI).

$$NNI(A_t, B_t) \equiv \frac{1}{OPR(A_t, B_t) - CPR(A_t, B_t)} \quad (2.92)$$

Mathematically, the index NNI is the reciprocal of the absolute prevalence increase.

Odds ratio (OR)

Definition 2.47 (Odds ratio (OR)).

Odds ratios as an appropriate measure for estimating the relative risk have become widely used in medical reports of case-control studies. The odds ratio (see also Fisher, 1935, p. 50) is defined (see also Cox, 1958) as the ratio of the odds of an event occurring in one group with respect to the odds of its occurring in another group. Odds (see also Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 273) ratio (OR) is a measure of association which quantifies the relationship between two binomial distributed random variables (exposure vs. outcome) and is related to Yule's (see also Yule and Pearson, 1900, p. 272) Q (see also Yule, 1912, p. 585/586). Two events A_t and B_t are regarded as independent if $OR(A_t, B_t) = 1$. Let

a_t = number of persons exposed to A_t and with disease B_t

b_t = number of persons exposed to A_t but without disease B_t

c_t = number of persons unexposed \bar{A}_t but with disease B_t

d_t = number of persons unexposed \bar{A}_t : and without disease B_t

$a_t + c_t$ = total number of persons with disease B_t (case-patients)

$b_t + d_t$ = total number of persons without disease B_t (controls).

Hereafter, consider the table 21. The odds' ratio (OR) is defined as

Table 21. The two by two table of random variables

		Conditioned/Outcome B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition/Exposure A_t	TRUE	a_t	b_t	A_t
	FALSE	c_t	d_t	\bar{A}_t
		B_t	\bar{B}_t	N_t

$$\begin{aligned}
 OR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t}{b_t} \right) / \left(\frac{c_t}{d_t} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.93}$$

Remark 2.5. Odds ratios can support logical fallacies and cause difficulties in drawing logically consistent conclusions. The chorus of voices is growing, which demand the immediate ending (see Sackett et al., 1996; Knol, 2012) of any use of Odds ratio.

Under conditions where $(b = 0)$, the measure of association odds ratio will collapse, because we need to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 2.93. However, according to today's rules of mathematics, a division by zero is neither allowed nor generally accepted as possible. It does no harm to remind ourselves that in the case $b = 0$ the event A_t is a sufficient condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of objective reality. In fact, it would be a failure not to recognize how dangerous and less valuable odds ratio is.

Under conditions where $(c = 0)$ odds ratio collapses too, because we need again to divide by zero, as can be seen at eq. 2.93. However, and again, today's rules of mathematics don't allow us a division by zero. In point of fact, in the case $c = 0$ it is more than necessary to point out that A_t is a necessary

condition of B_t . In other words, odds ratio or the cross-product ratio is not able to recognize elementary relationships of nature like necessary conditions. We can and need to overcome all the epistemological obstacles as backed by odds ratio entirety. Sooner rather than later, we should give up this measure of relationship completely.

Lemma 2.2 (THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELATIVE RISK (RR) AND ODDS RATIO (OR)). *The relationship between relative risk (RR_{nc}) and odds ratio (OR) is determined by the equation*

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(\frac{(NotA_t) \times b_t}{A_t \times d_t} \right) \times OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.94)$$

Proof. The relative risk RR_{nc} is defined as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{a_t \times (NotA_t)}{c_t \times A_t} \quad (2.95)$$

Rearranging, it is

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t}{(NotA_t)} \equiv a_t \quad (2.96)$$

Rearranging further, we obtain

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times c_t \times A_t \times d_t}{(NotA_t) \times b_t \times c_t} \equiv \frac{a_t \times d_t}{b_t \times c_t} \quad (2.97)$$

Equation before simplifies as

$$\frac{(RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc}) \times A_t \times d_t}{(NotA_t) \times b_t} \equiv OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.98)$$

or as

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \left(\frac{(NotA_t) \times b_t}{A_t \times d_t} \right) \times OR(A_t, B_t) \quad (2.99)$$

□

2.3. Statistical methods

The probability of the necessary (see [Barukčić, 2021c](#)) condition p(SINE) has been calculated and tested for statistical significance. The probability of the sufficient (see [Barukčić, 2021c](#)) condition p(IMP) has been calculated, the statistical significance of this relationship has been proofed. The chi-square goodness of fit test with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit a certain theoretical distribution in the population. The causal relationship k (see [Barukčić, 2021c](#)) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events/factors analysed. The hyper-geometric(see [Huygens and van Schooten, 1657](#); [Pearson, 1899](#); [Fisher, 1922](#); [Gonin, 1936](#)) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided significance of the causal relationship k . The study (design) bias has been controlled by IOI, the index of independence(see [Barukčić, 2019b](#)) and IOU, the index of unfairness(see [Barukčić, 2019a](#)). All the data were analysed using MS Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA). The p values less than 0.05 were considered to indicate a statistically significant difference.

2.4. Axioms

2.4.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis

In this context, we define axiom I as the expression

$$+ 1 = +1 \quad (2.100)$$

2.4.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis

In this context, axiom II or **lex contradictionis**, the negative of lex identitatis, or

$$+ 0 = +1 \quad (2.101)$$

and equally the most simple form of a contradiction formulated.

2.4.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis

$$\neg(0) \times 0 = 1 \quad (2.102)$$

where \neg denotes (logical (see [Boole, 1854](#)) or natural) negation (see [Royce, 1917](#); [Heinemann, 1943](#); [Ayer, 1952](#); [Hedwig, 1980](#); [Kunen, 1987](#); [Horn, 1989](#); [Wedin, 1990](#); [Koch, 1999](#); [Horn, 2001](#); [Speranza and Horn, 2010](#); [Förster and Melamed, 2012](#); [Newstadt, 2015](#)). In this context, there is some evidence that $\neg(1) \times 1 = 0$. In other words, it is $(\neg(1) \times 1) \times (\neg(0) \times 0) = 1$

3. Results

3.1. Without B19 IgG positivity no thyroid cancer

Etemadi et al. (see [Etemadi et al., 2017](#)) provided additional data on the serological B19 immunoglobulin G (IgG) status of patients and controls.

Theorem 3.1 (WITHOUT B19 IgG POSITIVITY NO THYROID CANCER).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis:

B19 IgG positivity **is** a necessary condition of thyroid cancer .

Alternative Hypothesis:

B19 IgG positivity **is not** a necessary condition of thyroid cancer .

Proof by the study of Etemadi et al. The study of Etemadi et al. (see [Etemadi et al., 2017](#)) provided data (see table 8) on the relationship between B19 IgG positivity and thyroid cancer . The study design (see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) has been highly unfair ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0,6875$). The causal relationship k is positive ($k = +0,2485$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= $0,150092507$) but not significant. Nonetheless, the data of the study of Etemadi et al. do support the Null-Hypothesis: **Without** B19 IgG positivity **no** thyroid cancer ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,979166667$; $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - B_t) = 0,027777778$; $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - A_t) = 0,333333333$). As a matter of course, based on the data of Etemadi et al. (see [Etemadi et al., 2017](#)) a B19 infection (detected by B19 immunoglobulin G) is a necessary condition of thyroid cancer. **Without** a B19 infection, **no** thyroid cancer. \square

3.2. Without a B19 infection, no thyroid cancer

Theorem 3.2 (WITHOUT A B19 INFECTION, NO THYROID CANCER).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis:

A B19 infection **is** a necessary condition of thyroid cancer .

Alternative Hypothesis:

A B19 infection **is not** a necessary condition of thyroid cancer .

Proof. The study of Wang et al. (see [Wang et al., 2008](#)) provided data (see table 3) on the relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer . The study design (see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) has been highly unfair ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0,5185$). Still, the causal relationship k is positive ($k = 0,6303$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= $1,85004E-05$) and highly statistically significant. The data of the study of Wang et al. do support the Null-Hypothesis: **Without** B19 DNA(PCR) positivity **no** thyroid cancer ($p(\text{SINE}) = 0,981481481$; $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - B_t) = 0,026315789$; $\tilde{\chi}^2(\text{SINE} - A_t) = 0,1$ p Value (SINE) = $0,018348104$).

Adamson et al. (see [Adamson et al., 2011](#)) provided data (see table 5) on the relationship between B19 capsid protein (ICH) and thyroid cancer, a control group is missed. Unfortunately, **the tumour surroundings, which are the perfect foundation for a control group**, have not been used for these purposes. Therefore, the study design (see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) cannot be judged. Based on the data of Adamson et al. (see [Adamson et al., 2011](#)), the causal relationship k cannot be calculated. Nonetheless,

under the assumption of a fair (see [Barukčić, 2019a](#)) study design, the calculation of the necessary condition is possible. As a consequence, the data of the study of Adamson et al. do support the Null-Hypothesis: **Without** B19 capsid protein (detected by ICH) **no** thyroid cancer (p (SINE) = 0,934782609 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,375 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 0,391304348).

The study of Etemadi et al. (see [Etemadi et al., 2017](#)) provided data (see table 6) on the relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer . The study design (see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) has been very unfair (p (IOU) = 0,4583). The control group was not appropriate enough. Theoretically it is possible to use **the tumour surroundings, which are the perfect foundation for a control group**, for PCR DNA analysis too. Besides of an inappropriate control group, the causal relationship k is positive ($k = +0,5822$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= 0,000180196) and highly significant. The data of the study of Etemadi et al. do support the Null-Hypothesis: **Without** B19 DNA(PCR) positivity **no** thyroid cancer (p (SINE) = 0,895833333 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — B_t) = 0,694444444 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE — A_t) = 1,785714286). The logical consequence is unavoidable. The data presented support the Null-Hypothesis: **Without** B19 positivity, **no** thyroid cancer. Parvovirus B19 is a necessary condition of thyroid cancer. \square

3.3. If B19 positivity of thyroid tissues, then thyroid cancer

Theorem 3.3 (IF B19 POSITIVITY OF THYROID TISSUES, THEN THYROID CANCER).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis:

B19 positivity of thyroid tissues **is** a sufficient condition of thyroid cancer .

Alternative Hypothesis:

B19 positivity of thyroid tissues **is not** a sufficient condition of thyroid cancer .

Proof. The study of Wang et al. (see [Wang et al., 2008](#)) provided data (see table 3) on the relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity of thyroid tissues and thyroid cancer . The study design (see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) has been very unfair (p (IOU) = 0,5185). Still, the causal relationship k is positive ($k = +0,6303$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= 1,85004E-05) and highly significant. The data of the study of Wang et al. do support the Null-Hypothesis: **If** B19 DNA(PCR) positivity of thyroid tissues **then** thyroid cancer (p (IMP) = **0,87037037** ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 1,113636364 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 3,088815789).

Due to missing data, the study of Adamson et al. (see [Adamson et al., 2011](#)) has not been used for these purposes.

The study of Etemadi et al. (see [Etemadi et al., 2017](#)) provided data (see table 6) on the relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity of thyroid tissues and thyroid cancer . The study design (see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) has been very unfair (p (IOU) = 0,4583). Nonetheless, the causal relationship k is positive ($k = +0,5822$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= 0,000180196) and highly significant. The data of the study of Etemadi et al. do support the Null-Hypothesis: **If** B19 DNA(PCR) positivity of thyroid tissues, **then** thyroid cancer (p (IMP) = **0,9375** ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — A_t) = 0,264705882 ; $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP — B_t) = 1,444444444). In other words, the studies presented support the Null-Hypothesis that a B19 infection of thyroid tissues, **is** a sufficient condition of thyroid cancer. In other words, **if** B19 infection of thyroid tissues, **then** thyroid cancer. \square

3.4. B19 infection is the cause of thyroid cancer

Theorem 3.4 (B19 INFECTION IS THE CAUSE OF THYROID CANCER).

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis:

B19 infection **is not** the cause of thyroid cancer .

Alternative Hypothesis:

B19 infection **is** the cause of thyroid cancer .

Proof. Wang et al. (see [Wang et al., 2008](#)) published data (see table 3) on the relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer . The study design (see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) has been highly unfair ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0,5185$). The causal relationship k is positive ($k = +0,6303$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= $1,85004E-05$) and highly significant. The study of Wang et al. has provided evidence of a necessary condition relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer (see table 3). The same study did provide additional evidence of a sufficient conditions relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer (see table 3). Altogether, the foundations to analyse the data for causal relationship are given. The data of the study of Wang et al. do not support the null-hypothesis that B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer are independent of each other. Therefore, we do reject the null-hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. B19 DNA(PCR) positivity is the cause of thyroid cancer ($k = +0,630288629$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= $1,85004E-05$).

The study group of Etemadi et al. (see [Etemadi et al., 2017](#)) published data (see table 6) on the relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer. The study design (see [Barukčić, 2019a,b](#)) has been very unfair ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0,4583$). The causal relationship k is positive ($k = +0,5822$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= $0,000180196$) and highly significant. The study of Etemadi et al. has provided evidence of a necessary condition relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer (see table 6). The same study did provide additional evidence of a sufficient conditions relationship between B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer (see table 6). Altogether, the foundations to analyse the data for causal relationship are given. The data of the study of Etemadi et al. do not support the null-hypothesis that B19 DNA(PCR) positivity and thyroid cancer are independent of each other. Therefore, we do reject the null-hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. B19 DNA(PCR) positivity is the cause of thyroid cancer ($k = +0,582181736$; p Value right tailed (HGD)= $0,000180196$).

□

4. Discussion

Human parvoviruses, derived from the Latin word “parvus” meaning small (*ca.25nm*), are prevalent worldwide(see [Qiu et al., 2017](#)). B19 is highly infectious and causes a wide range of pathological changes: persistent anemia in immunocompromised patients, fifth disease in children(see [Brown and Young, 1997](#)), transient aplastic crises, hydrops fetalis in pregnant women et cetera. It should be emphasized that the full spectrum of parvovirus disease in humans has yet to be established completely. Under these conditions, it may not be an easy task to determine a causal relationship between events like a viral infection with B19 and thyroid cancer. However, such a task is not impossible either. Another challenge is that various forms of biases pose a threat to the validity of meta-analysis. Studies

provided more and more evidence that “... for most study designs and settings, it is more likely for a research claim to be false than true ”(see Ioannidis, 2005). However, the presence of bias inside the data of the studies analysed has been controlled and detected by the index of unfairness and the index of independence. Funnel plots(see Egger et al., 1997) are potentially misleading(see Tang and Liu, 2000) and have not been used in this context. An additional difficulty was the small sample size of the studies meta-analysed. To be fair, it is self-evident that the results from these analyses should be treated with considerable caution. However, even if further work is required to investigate the exact role of B19 infection in thyroid cancer, the result of this study supports a preliminary and inescapable conclusion.

5. Conclusion

Parvovirus B19 is the cause of thyroid cancer.

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6. Patient consent for publication

Not required.

Conflict of interest statement

No conflict of interest to declare.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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